

Use of Americium and Curium fractions of minor actinides for the production of heat sources for radioisotope thermoelectric generators

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Abstract

The article considers the possibility of using the mixed (Am, Cm)-fraction extracted from minor actinides (MA) for large-scale production of powerful heat sources for space radioisotope thermoelectric generators (RTG). Such a choice of the MA fraction removes the limitation on the proportion of ²³⁶Pu in plutonium and leaves only a limitation on the proportion of ²³⁸Pu (above 80%). The irradiation of the (Am, Cm) mixture and the separated Am-fraction of MA are considered and compared. The irradiated material was placed in the central assembly of the VVER-1000 light-water power reactor core. It is proposed to remove only fission products (FP) from the irradiated material and to use the remaining three-component (Pu, Am, Cm) mixture as a heat source in the RTG. It has been shown that the mixed (Am, Cm)-fraction of MA is a preferable starting material compared to the Am-fraction since it provides the higher specific heat release of the produced three-component (Pu, Am, Cm) mixture at comparable rates of plutonium production and its isotopic compositions.

Keywords

minor actinides; americium; curium; radioisotope thermoelectric generators; light-water power reactors

Introduction

It is known that the composition of spent nuclear fuel (SNF) of light-water power reactors includes both materials useful for nuclear power engineering (uranium and plutonium isotopes) and materials useless for it (radioactive fission products and transuranium elements, namely minor actinides). However, the uselessness of minor actinides (MA), classified as transuranium radioactive waste, actually raises certain doubts since there is a possibility of their use as starting materials for the production of powerful heat sources.

Let us assume that SNF reprocessing technology includes the following steps:

1. Separation of uranium and plutonium for subsequent re-fabrication of fresh fuel composition of nuclear power reactors.
2. Separation of FP for subsequent ultimate disposal in geological repositories as radioactive wastes.
3. Separation of MA containing three fractions: neptunium (²³⁷Np), americium (²⁴¹Am and ²⁴³Am) and curium (²⁴⁴Cm and ²⁴⁵Cm).

Like fission products, MA can also be classified as useless radioactive wastes, suitable either for burning in nuclear reactors, i.e., converting them into FP, or immediately for ultimate disposal in geological repositories. However, it is also possible to regard MA as a useful material suitable for the production of heat sources for RTG. Such generators are currently widely used as energy sources in spacecrafts. The possibility for useful application of MA is determined by the following properties:

1. The isotope ^{237}Np is the closest neutron precursor for plutonium isotope ^{238}Pu , the powerful heat source (560 W/kg), via the $^{237}\text{Np}(n,\gamma)^{238}\text{Pu}$ reaction.
2. The isotopes ^{241}Am and especially ^{244}Cm are themselves intense sources of thermal energy (112 W/kg for ^{241}Am and 2780 W/kg for ^{244}Cm). In addition, the isotope ^{243}Am , a relatively weak heat source, can feed ^{244}Cm via $^{243}\text{Am}(n,\gamma)^{244}\text{Cm}$ reaction.

In this connection, it is possible to use directly the Am-fraction of MA as a heat source for RTG, as well as to subject MA to neutron irradiation in nuclear reactors to produce ^{238}Pu via two channels: $^{237}\text{Np}(n,\gamma)^{238}\text{Pu}$ and $^{241}\text{Am}(n,\gamma)^{242}\text{Cm}(\alpha)^{238}\text{Pu}$. However, direct use of the Am-fraction in RTG requires complex and expensive extraction of americium from MA. As for neutron irradiation of MA to produce ^{238}Pu , the $^{237}\text{Np}(n,\gamma)$ reaction leading to the formation of the target isotope is accompanied by the $^{237}\text{Np}(n,2n)$ reaction leading to the formation of the undesirable isotope ^{236}Pu , an intense source of high-energy γ -radiation by its decay products. That is why plutonium may be regarded as the RTG-grade material only if the ^{236}Pu fraction is below 2 ppm. This limitation could be met, for example, by surrounding the Np-containing target with a material that would be able to weaken significantly the flux of high-energy neutrons, which are capable of initiating the threshold $^{237}\text{Np}(n,2n)$ reaction.

In publications (Johnson 2017; Daily and McDuffee 2020; Dustin and Borrelli 2021; Shmelev et al. 2023a, 2023b, 2024a, 2024b; Green et al. 2024), the possibility for neutron irradiation of the Np-fraction and the mixed (Np, Am)-fraction of MA in VVER-type light-water power reactors was studied. The aim of the research was to evaluate the productivity scale of the RTG-grade plutonium (^{236}Pu content is below 2 ppm, ^{238}Pu content is above 80%). The main difficulty in producing such plutonium turned out to be associated with the limitation on the proportion of ^{236}Pu . To meet this condition, it was necessary to surround the fuel assembly with the irradiated MA by a protective layer of assemblies containing, for example, natural lead. It is evident that such a strong change in the structure of the reactor core, although it provides large-scale production of a valuable heat source, complicates seriously the operating conditions and worsens the economic profitability of the power reactor. However, if we exclude the Np-fraction from the MA composition, the ^{236}Pu problem disappears completely, since there are no

chains of nuclear reactions leading from americium and curium isotopes to ^{236}Pu . Accordingly, there is no need to surround the irradiated material with any protective layers. At present, there are already quite effective radiochemical technologies for Np extraction from the SNF compositions (Nefedov et al. 1987).

In this paper, we consider a possibility to use the mixed (Am, Cm)-fraction and the separated Am-fraction of MA for large-scale production of RTG-grade plutonium in the light-water power reactor VVER-1000. The use of such starting materials removes the limitation on the proportion of ^{236}Pu and leaves only the limitation on the proportion of ^{238}Pu (above 80%). The latter is associated with the non-proliferation of nuclear weapons (INFCIRC/153 2008) and the need for a sufficiently high power of the heat source in the RTG.

Mathematical model

Calculations of the neutron-physical parameters of the reactor and the kinetics of the isotopic composition of the fuel were carried out with the application of the computer code TIME26 for the cylindrical model of VVER-1000 in 26-group diffusion approximation (Kuzmin et al. 2015). The constant provision of the computer code is based on the evaluated nuclear data file ABBN (Abagyan et al. 1981). The authors' decision to use the deterministic computer code TIME26 was explained by desirable decreasing the computer time expenses for the multi-variant studies. Certainly, authors are planning to perform the more accurate computations with application of the high-precision Monte Carlo code SERPENT2.

The geometric zone-wise model of the VVER-1000 reactor core included 169 fuel assemblies. A zone R-Z reactor model was considered, comprising eight annular layers of fuel assemblies, separated from the reactor vessel by a water layer. Some other parameters of the reactor model are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Additional parameters of the reactor model

Model order	2D
Pitch of spatial mesh, cm	1.5
Time step in determination of fuel burn-up, days	30
Thermal power, MW	3200
Convergence tolerance for source iteration	10^{-6}
Convergence tolerance for criticality condition	10^{-5}
Boundary condition in the reactor center	$\nabla\varphi = 0$
Boundary condition on the external reactor border	$\varphi = 0$

Hexagonal fuel assemblies of the VVER-1000 reactor contain 312 fuel rods in triangular lattice. Fuel layout for the VVER-1000 assembly is shown in Fig. 1, and its main parameters are presented in Table 2.

The diagram of neutron reactions leading to the plutonium production from MA is shown in Fig. 2.

In the calculations with one-year irradiation time, decays with too short and too long half-lives were ignored.

Table 2. Some parameters of VVER-1000 assembly

Fuel – enriched uranium dioxide (4.4% ²³⁵ U), density, g/cm ³	10.7
Fuel rod cladding – 99% Zr-1% Nb alloy, density, g/cm ³	6.5
Number of fuel elements	312
Coolant – light water, density, g/cm ³	0.73
Flat-to-flat size of hexagonal fuel assembly, cm	23.4
Diameter of fuel pellet, mm	7.57
Diameter of central hole, mm	1.40
Thickness of fuel-to-cladding gap, mm	0.075
Thickness of cladding, mm	0.65
Pitch of the triangular set of fuel elements, mm	12.75
Height of the fuel column, cm	353

Figure 1. Fuel layout for the VVER-1000 assembly. 1 – Fuel cell with UO₂; 2 – Fuel cell with U-Gd fuel; 3 – Guide tube cell; 4 – Central tube cell; 5 – water.

Calculations of heat source production for RTG

It was assumed that the irradiation device, placed in the center of the reactor core, is a standard fuel assembly of the VVER-1000 reactor. In the fuel elements of the irradiation device, the enriched uranium dioxide is replaced by a mixture of americium and curium dioxides (AmO₂/CmO₂) in proportions corresponding to the percentages of the Am-fraction and Cm-fraction in the MA (MA do not contain the previously extracted Np-fraction, Table 3). Geometrical parameters of fuel rods in the irradiation device and material of the fuel cladding corresponded with typical fuel rods of the VVER-1000 reactor and presented in Table 2.

It is evident that long-term SNF cooling before reprocessing leads to a significant change in the isotopic composition of MA. The mass and proportion of ²⁴¹Am increase significantly due to the relatively fast β-decay of ²⁴¹Pu (T_{1/2} = 14.35 years), and the mass and proportion of ²⁴⁴Cm decrease due to its α-decay (T_{1/2} = 18.1 years). The masses of long-lived isotopes ²⁴³Am (T_{1/2} = 7380 years) and ²⁴⁵Cm (T_{1/2} = 8500 years) do not change with such

“Americium” branching:

Radiative capture of neutrons by the isotope ²⁴¹Am proceeds through the following two channels:

²⁴¹Am(n,γ)^{242g}Am with a probability of 90.3% and ²⁴¹Am(n,γ)^{242m}Am with a probability of 9.7%.

Fast decay of the isotope ^{242g}Am (T_{1/2} = 16 hours) also proceeds through two channels:

^{242g}Am(β-decay)²⁴²Cm with a probability of 83% and ^{242g}Am(electronic capture)²⁴²Pu with a probability of 17%. Considering the decay of ^{242g}Am to be instantaneous, this section of the chain can be represented as follows:

Figure 2. Isotopic transitions for plutonium production from MA.

Table 3. Mass characteristics of irradiation device and isotopic composition of MA in VVER-1000 SNF (Andryushin and Yudin 2010)

Target form	AmO ₂ /CmO ₂		
Total MA mass per device with lattice pitch of 60 mm, kg	22.3		
MA mass per rod, kg	1.17		
Mass density of MA oxide, g/cm ³	10.5		
MA oxide stoichiometry	MAO ₂		
Isotopes	SNF cooling time before reprocessing, years		
	0	10	30
²⁴¹ Am, g/t SNF	65.4	760	1424
²⁴³ Am, g/t SNF	150	150	150
²⁴⁴ Cm, g/t SNF	44	30	14
²⁴⁵ Cm, g/t SNF	2	2	2
²⁴¹ Am, %	25.0	80.7	89.6
²⁴³ Am, %	57.4	15.9	9.4
²⁴⁴ Cm, %	16.8	3.2	0.9
²⁴⁵ Cm, %	0.8	0.2	0.1

SNF cooling times, but their proportions in the MA composition decrease noticeably. Having known the specific heat release of americium and curium isotopes, it is possible to calculate the total specific heat release of their mixture Q_a for different SNF cooling times (Table 4).

It is clear that the main role in the heat release of the (Am, Cm)-mixture is played by the isotopes ²⁴¹Am and ²⁴⁴Cm with a very weak contribution from ²⁴³Am. The

Table 4. Specific heat release of (Am, Cm)-fraction

Specific heat release, W/kg	SNF cooling time before reprocessing, years		
	0	10	30
Full Q_{α}	501.0	180.8	125.8
Contribution of ^{241}Am	27.8	90.1	100.0
Contribution of ^{243}Am	3.6	1.0	0.6
Contribution of ^{244}Cm	469.6	89.7	25.2

obtained values of the specific heat release of the (Am, Cm) mixture already allow using this mixture in RTG, even without neutron irradiation in nuclear reactors for the production of more powerful heat sources.

However, after irradiation in a nuclear reactor, ^{238}Pu appears in the (Am, Cm) mixture, a strong source of heat release (560 W/kg). Calculations showed that the best specific heat releases of the (Pu, Am, Cm)-mixture, plutonium production rate and isotopic composition were obtained for a spacious enough lattice of the MA-containing fuel elements (MA-rods) in the irradiation device. Layout of MA-rods with a lattice pitch of 60 mm is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. MA-rod lattice with pitch of 60 mm in irradiation device. 1 – water; 2 – MA-rod.

The main parameters of the MA-rods after one-year irradiation in VVER-1000 for a lattice pitch of 60 mm are presented below.

The data presented in Table 5 allow us to draw the following conclusions:

Table 5. Main parameters of irradiated (Am, Cm)-mixture

Parameters	SNF cooling time before reprocessing, years		
	0	10	30
Full Q_{α} , W/kg	695.5	262.9	194.5
Contribution of ^{238}Pu , W/kg	28.9	57.1	60.2
Contribution of ^{241}Am , W/kg	19.9	75.0	84.2
Contribution of ^{243}Am , W/kg	3.2	0.9	0.6
Contribution of ^{243}Cm , W/kg	0.4	0.5	0.5
Contribution of ^{244}Cm , W/kg	643.1	129.4	49.0
Pu, kg/year	1.44	2.8	2.9
$^{238}\text{Pu} / \text{Pu}$, %	79.4	81.2	81.3
Pu / (Am, Cm), %	6.44	12.5	13.1

1. Irradiation of the initial (Am, Cm)-mixture in VVER-1000 leads to a noticeable increase in the specific heat release of the resulting (Pu, Am, Cm)-mixture due to an increase in the contribution of ^{238}Pu .
2. The transition to irradiation of MA extracted from SNF with the longer cooling time reduces the specific heat release of the (Pu, Am, Cm)-mixture due to a rapid decrease in the contribution of ^{244}Cm .
3. The transition to irradiation of MA extracted from SNF with the longer cooling time significantly increases the rate of Pu production (up to ~ 3 kg/year), the proportion of ^{238}Pu in plutonium (up to $\sim 81\%$) and the proportion of plutonium in the irradiated mixture (up to $\sim 13\%$).

Thus, the longer SNF cooling time before reprocessing, on the one hand, reduces the specific heat release of the irradiated material, and on the other hand, improves the main parameters of RTG-grade plutonium in the terms of its production rate and isotopic composition.

Nevertheless, if it will be decided to arrange a complicated radiochemical extraction of a pure Am fraction from the MA composition and to use the extracted Am-fraction as the starting material, the following results were obtained (Tables 6, 7).

Table 6. Specific heat release of (Am)-fraction before irradiation

Specific heat release, W/kg	SNF cooling time before reprocessing, years		
	0	10	30
Full Q_{α}	38.1	94.2	101.6
Contribution of ^{241}Am	33.8	93.2	101.0
Contribution of ^{243}Am	4.3	1.0	0.6

Table 7. Main parameters of irradiated (Am)-fraction

Parameters	SNF cooling time before reprocessing, years		
	0	10	30
Full Q_{α} , W/kg	246.3	178.3	170.6
Contribution of ^{238}Pu , W/kg	29.7	57.1	60.1
Contribution of ^{241}Am , W/kg	25.5	78.1	85.2
Contribution of ^{243}Am , W/kg	3.9	0.9	0.6
Contribution of ^{243}Cm , W/kg	0.4	0.5	0.5
Contribution of ^{244}Cm , W/kg	186.8	41.7	24.2
Pu, kg/year	1.48	2.8	2.9
$^{238}\text{Pu} / \text{Pu}$, %	80.1	81.3	81.4
Pu / (Am, Cm), %	6.6	12.5	13.1

After one-year irradiation in VVER-1000, the main parameters of the irradiated Am fraction will take the following values.

If we compare the specific heat release of the mixed (Am, Cm) fraction and the separated Am fraction before irradiation in VVER-1000 (see Tables 4, 6), the advantage of the (Am, Cm) fraction becomes obvious, mainly due to the presence of the isotope ^{244}Cm .

If we compare the main parameters of the mixed (Am, Cm) fraction and the separated Am fraction after one-year irradiation in VVER-1000 (see Tables 5, 7), the preference of the (Am, Cm) fraction becomes even more obvious. The

specific heat release of the irradiated (Am, Cm) fraction is significantly higher, and the production rates and isotopic compositions of plutonium differ little from similar data for the irradiated Am fraction. Thus, the complex and expensive extraction of the Am fraction from the MA composition for the needs of space RTG may prove unnecessary.

As for the use of SNF with different cooling times before reprocessing (see Tables 4–7), the following conclusions can be made. The shorter the cooling time of SNF, the higher the specific heat release of the mixed (Am, Cm) fraction both before and after irradiation compared to the specific heat release of the separated Am fraction, mainly due to the contribution of ^{244}Cm . However, the use of MA extracted from SNF with the longer cooling time leads to a significant increase in the production rate of RTG-grade plutonium. This increase is associated with an increase in the proportion of ^{241}Am , the main source of plutonium production, in the MA. The plutonium extraction from the resulting three-component (Pu, Am, Cm) mixture for subsequent use in space RTG is a too complex and expensive process, and also inexpedient, since it will reduce the heat release of the remaining mixture.

It is noteworthy the other important difference between the two irradiated materials: the mixed (Am, Cm) fraction and the separated Am fraction. The specific heat release of the irradiated (Am, Cm) fraction is significantly higher than that of the irradiated Am fraction (695.5 W/kg versus 246.3 W/kg at $T_{\text{cool}} = 0$). This advantage is explained by the larger proportion of ^{244}Cm and its short half-life. However, it is the short half-life of ^{244}Cm that leads to a faster decrease in the heat release of the irradiated (Am, Cm) fraction. The times for the heat release to decrease for the irradiated materials to the level of heat release before irradiation are given in Table 8.

Table 8. Heat release reduction time

Parameters	SNF cooling time before reprocessing, years		
	0	10	30
Q_a (Am,Cm), W/kg, before irradiation	501.0	180.8	125.8
Q_a (Pu,Am,Cm), W/kg, after irradiation	695.5	262.9	194.5
T (after→ before), years	9.3	20.7	50.5
Q_a (Am), W/kg, before irradiation	38.1	94.2	101.6
Q_a (Pu,Am,Cm), W/kg, after irradiation	246.3	178.3	170.6
T (after→ before), years	121.4	100.2	98.1

Table 9. Prompt neutron lifetime and effective delayed neutron fraction when replacing uranium fuel with an (AmO₂/CmO₂) mixture in the central fuel assembly of a VVER-1000 reactor. The data relate to loading the reactor with fresh fuel. For the (AmO₂/CmO₂) mixture, the variants of the Am and Cm proportions corresponding to Tcool=0, 10 and 30 years of VVER-1000 spent fuel were considered.

Parameter	Uranium fuel	(AmO ₂ /CmO ₂)-mixture, Tcool = 0	(AmO ₂ /CmO ₂)-mixture, Tcool = 10 years	(AmO ₂ /CmO ₂)-mixture, Tcool = 30 years
Prompt neutron lifetime, sec	1.62×10^{-5}	1.63×10^{-5}	1.63×10^{-5}	1.63×10^{-5}
Effective delayed neutron fraction	8.62×10^{-3}	8.60×10^{-3}	8.60×10^{-3}	8.60×10^{-3}

Table 10. Reactivity coefficients for fuel temperature (K_D) and coolant temperature (K_{cool}) when replacing uranium fuel with (AmO₂/CmO₂)-mixture in the central fuel assembly of the VVER-1000 reactor.

Parameter	Uranium fuel	(AmO ₂ /CmO ₂)-mixture, Tcool = 0	(AmO ₂ /CmO ₂)-mixture, Tcool = 10 years	(AmO ₂ /CmO ₂)-mixture, Tcool = 30 years
K_D , 1/°C	-4.76×10^{-2}	-4.74×10^{-2}	-4.75×10^{-2}	-4.76×10^{-2}
K_{cool} , 1/°C	-9.10×10^{-5}	-9.08×10^{-5}	-9.07×10^{-5}	-9.07×10^{-5}

The data in this table allow us to draw the following conclusion: (Am, Cm) fraction provides higher heat release, but this level decreases faster to the level before irradiation. In other words, the (Am, Cm) fraction is capable of providing higher heat release but for a shorter time than the Am fraction.

Assessing the impact of (AmO₂/CmO₂) mixture in the central fuel assembly on the safety parameters of a VVER-1000 reactor

The impact of replacing uranium fuel with an (AmO₂/CmO₂) mixture in the central fuel assembly of a VVER-1000 reactor on its safety parameters is examined. Tables 9, 10 present the dynamic parameters of reactor safety.

The data in the tables show an insignificant effect of replacing uranium fuel with a (AmO₂/CmO₂) mixture in the central fuel assembly of the VVER-1000 reactor. Despite this, the issues of safe operation of the reactor when the (AmO₂/CmO₂) mixture is placed instead of uranium fuel deserves further comprehensive justification.

Conclusions

- 1) It is proposed to use the mixed (Am, Cm) fraction and the separated Am-fraction of MA for the production of powerful heat sources suitable for space RTG. The exclusion of the Np fraction from the starting material eliminates the problem of high-energy γ -radiation emitted by ^{236}Pu decay products. As a result, there is no need to surround the irradiated material with any protective layers.
- 2) It is proposed to separate only FP after irradiation of the starting materials and to directly use the remaining three-component (Pu, Am, Cm) mixture as a heat source for RTG.
- 3) The mixed (Am, Cm) fraction of MA is shown to be preferable as compared with the separated Am fraction, since the former provides the higher heat release of the resulting product. The main reason is

- the greater contribution of ^{244}Cm , which is already part of the starting material and is fed during irradiation with americium isotopes. This preference makes the complex and expensive separation of the Am fraction from the MA composition unnecessary.
- 4) The shorter cooling time of the SNF from which the starting material is extracted, the higher the specific heat release of the mixed (Am, Cm) fraction both before and after irradiation compared to the specific heat release of the Am fraction. However, the use of MA extracted from SNF with the longer cooling time leads to a significant increase in the production rate of RTG-grade plutonium and to a slowdown in the decline in heat release by the (Pu, Am, Cm)-mixture.
 - 5) Due to the absence of a problem with ^{236}Pu for the mixed (Am, Cm)-fraction of MA, it seems appropriate to consider the possibility of producing powerful heat sources for RTG via irradiation of the (Am, Cm)-fraction of MA in fast reactors.
 - 6) After irradiation of the mixed (Am,Cm)-fraction or the separated Am-fraction the following two

variants are possible, namely either recovery of RTG-grade plutonium from (Pu,Am,Cm,FP)-mixture or removal of only FP with production of three-component (Pu,Am,Cm)-mixture. The second option is evidently preferable from the radiochemistry point of view. However, (Pu,Am,Cm)-mixture can not be used in long-term space missions because of relatively short half-life of ^{244}Cm .

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